

Online Learning Survey

Have you ever used an online resource to learn something?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Which of the following topics have you tried to learn about through online resources? (Check all that apply)

- History (1)
- Literature/Poetry (2)
- Graphic Design (Image Editing, Animation, etc.) (3)
- Arts (Music, Theater, Film, Dance, Visual Arts) (4)
- Religion/Ethics/Philosophy (5)
- Politics (Social Activism, Community Organizing) (6)
- Social science (Psychology, Economics, Sociology, Political Science, etc.) (7)
- Law (8)
- Medicine/Nursing/Pharmacology (9)
- Math (Algebra, Geometry, Statistics, etc.) (10)
- Science (Engineering, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, etc.) (11)
- Programming (Data Science, Web Development, etc.) (12)
- Languages (13)

- Travel/geography (14)
- Personal Health/Health Care (15)
- Online safety, security, or privacy (16)
- How-to (around the house, cooking & baking, arts & crafts) (18)
- Physical Fitness/Exercise (19)
- Makeup/Fashion (20)
- Other: (21) _____
- None of the above (22)

Display This Question:

*If Which of the following topics have you tried to learn about through online resources? (Check all...
!= None of the above*

*Carry Forward Selected Choices from "Which of the following topics have you tried to learn about through
online resources? (Check all that apply)"*

Which topics did you learn about using each of these resources? (Check all that apply)

	History (1)	Literature/Poetry (2)	Graphic Design (Image Editing, Animation, etc.) (3)	Arts (Music, Theater, Film, Dance, Visual Arts) (4)	Religion/Ethics/Philosophy (5)	Politics (Social Activism, Community Organizing) (6)
Watched a video (e.g YouTube) (1)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Read Wikipedia (2)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Read an informational article (WebMD, a museum website, a dictionary website) (3)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Read a how-to-guide (e.g., WikiHow, BetterExplained.com) (4)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Used an interactive tutorial (e.g., Duolingo, KhanAcademy, Codecademy) (5)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Used a practice exam website (e.g., Magoosh, Chegg) (6)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Used materials from a course (e.g., online lecture slides, MIT OpenCourseWare) (7)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Took an online course (8)

Read answers to questions on a forum (e.g., Reddit, StackOverflow, Facebook Group, Yahoo Answers) (9)

Asked questions in an online discussion community or forum (e.g., Reddit, StackOverflow, Facebook Group, Yahoo Answers) (10)